

“METHODS OF WORD FORMATION IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES”

Uzakova Risbiyke

2nd year master student of the speciality Linguistics: English language, Karakalpak
State University

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Abstract. Comparing noun formation by affixation in English and Karakalpak can provide insights into the similarities and differences between these two languages. Affixation is the process of adding prefixes or suffixes to a root word to create a new word with a different meaning. That's why, the article presents the comparative study of noun formation by affixation method in English and Karakalpak languages.

Keywords: word formation, noun formation, affixation, method, suffix, English, Karakalpak.

Comparing the use of affixes in English and Karakalpak can also reveal differences in the way these languages express grammatical relationships. For example, English uses prepositions to indicate the relationship between nouns and other elements in a sentence, while Karakalpak uses postpositions. Additionally, English has a complex system of verb tenses and moods, while Karakalpak has a simpler system with fewer distinctions [2].

In both English and Karakalpak, affixation is a common method of forming nouns. The suffix -ness is used in English to form abstract nouns indicating a state or quality, such as happiness and sadness. In Karakalpak, the suffix -lıq is used for a similar purpose, forming nouns like ashlıq (hunger) and qızlıq (maidenhood).

The suffix -ment in English is used to form nouns indicating an action or process, such as development and agreement. Similarly, the suffix -lik in Karakalpak is used to form nouns indicating a quality or action, such as mártlik (bravery).

The suffix -ity in English is used to form abstract nouns indicating a state or quality, such as equality and humanity. In Karakalpak, the suffix -at is used for a similar purpose, forming nouns like jasarat (courage) and taqat (patience) [4, 97-100].

The suffixes -tion and -sion in English are used to form nouns indicating an action or process, such as education and decision. In Karakalpak, the suffix -shì is used for a similar purpose, forming nouns like temirshi.

Finally, the suffixes -er and -or in English are used to form nouns indicating a person or thing that performs an action or has a certain quality, such as teacher and actor. These suffixes are not commonly used in Karakalpak.

English:

1. -ness: happiness, sadness
2. -ment: development, agreement
3. -ity: equality, humanity
4. -tion/-sion: education, decision
5. -er/-or: teacher, actor

Karakalpak:

1. ashlıq (hunger), qızlıq (maidenhood)
2. mártlik (bravery), azatlıq (freedom)

3. jasarat (courage), taqat (patience)
4. basliq (leader), qaraqshı (guardian)
5. jaza (punishment), qarar (decision) [5]

The comparison of noun formation by affixation method in English and Karakalpak is important for several reasons. Firstly, it can help learners to understand the different rules and patterns for forming nouns in each language. This can be particularly useful for individuals who are learning both languages at the same time, as it can help them to identify similarities and differences between the two languages [3].

Secondly, the comparison of noun formation in different languages can help learners to develop a deeper understanding of the structure and usage of each language. By identifying the specific suffixes used and the rules for their application, learners can gain a more nuanced understanding of how to use each language effectively.

Thirdly, comparing noun formation in different languages can help to identify commonalities and differences across languages. This can be particularly useful for individuals who are multilingual, as it can help them to identify patterns and similarities between the languages they are studying.

Conclusion. Overall, the comparison of noun formation by affixation method in English and Karakalpak is an important tool for language learners. It can help them to develop a deeper understanding of each language, as well as identify commonalities and differences between different languages.

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